

FROM EUROPEAN GROUND MOTION SERVICE TO DIFFERENTIAL DEFORMATION MAP FOR BUILDINGS

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ABSTRACT

Multi-temporal synthetic aperture radar interferometry is nowadays a well-developed remote sensing technique for monitoring Earth's surface deformation. The European Ground Motion Service (EGMS) is an important component of ground deformation monitoring in Europe, which offers consistent, accurate, and annually updated information about ground displacements related to both natural and anthropogenic phenomena. The policy of providing EGMS products free of charge enables us to leverage the data and develop tools to identify buildings and urban structures that are vulnerable to damage due to differential movement. The tool described in this paper facilitates the generation of a differential deformation map for individual buildings by computing the spatial gradient of deformation for each building and then classifying them into distinct classes according to their gradient values. To demonstrate the reliability and trustworthiness of identified buildings, an uncertainty analysis was performed. Its output includes the relationship between the ratio of average-to-standard deviation of gradient and the density of points in each building. The proposed approach was tested with EGMS data over the area of Catalunya (Spain) from 2015 to 2021. A total of 308 buildings were identified as vulnerable to damage, with around half of them classified as "Low" gradient intensity. This map can serve as the initial step required for an in-depth analysis and risk assessment, aiming to mitigate risks and maintain the stability and safety of buildings.

Keywords— *EGMS, differential deformation map, spatial gradient of deformation, damage.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Urban structures and buildings are sensitive to movements caused by ground natural or anthropogenic phenomena. The main goal of building risk analysis is to identify potential vulnerabilities and develop strategies to mitigate or eliminate risks [1]. The spatial and temporal characterization of land displacement is important in

understanding the process and risk management in urban environments. Specifically, differential spatial movement causes cracks and structural damage to appear in urban infrastructure/structure, while spatially uniform land movement does not cause immediate structural damage [1], [2]. Creating differential deformation maps for buildings enables us to identify local deformations that affect single structures as well as obtain consistent and reliable information about spatial gradients in structures since it has been observed that serious damage to man-made structures and infrastructures frequently occurs in correlation with high deformation gradient values. By monitoring, identifying, and addressing risks proactively, building owners, managers, and urban planners can create a safer environment and reduce the potential for harm [1]. Over the past few years, remote sensing techniques such as multi-temporal Differential Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (DInSAR) have been used to monitor and measure ground deformation in both urban and rural areas. Thanks to the PSI technique which can maintain the full resolution of input SAR images and is well-suited for structures and infrastructure analysis and monitoring. PSI also offers the advantage of sensitivity to small deformations, with a velocity precision of approximately 1 mm/yr [3].

The European ground motion service (EGMS) is part of the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service's product portfolio. Its main objective is to provide consistent and accurate information about ground displacements related to both natural and human-induced phenomena across Europe. EGMS is based on Sentinel-1 data processed at full resolution and it consists of a baseline product, which ranges from 2015 to the end of 2021, and annual updates [4]. The EGMS has three product levels, and we used the Basic level in this research. The Basic level is made up of geocoded line of sight (LOS) deformation velocity maps in ascending (ASC) and descending (DES) orbits, with measurements referencing a local point [4]. EGMS data have a policy of free and open access. They are available to any users at <https://egms.land.copernicus.eu/>. Although

EGMS offers tools for visualization, analysis, and download of massive datasets of deformation products, analysis of them can be challenging and time-consuming. The novelty of this work lies in the implementation of a methodology and the development of a tool that exploits EGMS displacement maps in order to identify buildings and urban structures that are susceptible to damage caused by differential deformation. The proposed methodology works at a single-building scale, by automatically selecting the deformation data that belong to the buildings and assessing the differential deformation (spatial gradient of deformation) affecting each specific building. The methodology has been tested over the area of Catalonia (Spain) using 33 datasets of the Basic level of EGMS displacement map from 2017 to 2021.

2. METHODOLOGY

Here we present a novel tool to exploit the wide-area displacement maps of EGMS data, with the final aim of identifying buildings and urban structures that may be vulnerable to damage. The proposed methodology considers the spatial gradient of deformation as the main factor causing buildings' damage and categorizes buildings into different groups based on their gradient intensity.

The Differential software tool was developed using Python, and the required input data for the procedure includes a displacement map of the study area and building polygons. Figure 1 shows the complete flowchart of the proposed methodology. In this context, the primary input is the PSI displacement map from EGMS, which includes the mean velocity of deformation in the LOS direction and the height of Measurement Points (MPs). The secondary input is an ESRI shapefile containing building polygons, like the OpenStreetMap dataset. This method can be used on either a single building dataset with a limited number of MPs or a wider region with millions of MPs.

The resulting output consists of a differential deformation map for buildings. All identified buildings are colored based on the intensity of spatial gradient of deformation which shows the potential damage of building. They are available to any users at <https://www.openstreetmap.org/>. In the analysis section, there are three important steps, starting from finding the MPs within buildings, computing

the spatial gradient of deformation for each building, and then building classification based on their gradient intensity. Here we intend to briefly describe the steps:

- 1) The procedure involves selecting MPs that belong to the building while ignoring data from other constructions or reflective objects. A buffer of an appropriate size is estimated by the range and azimuth values from EGMS data to set around the polygon perimeters to account for geolocation uncertainties for MPs [5]. The height of MPs is also checked to ensure that the chosen MPs belong to the building. Furthermore, MPs were filtered in order to detect and delete isolated and noise-affected points. These works are carried out to ensure a precise analysis and accurate gradient computations in each building's polygon.

- 2) Gradient calculation initiates when at least five MPs must have velocities exceeding ± 3 (mm/yr) in each polygon, otherwise the polygon will be excluded. This step begins by converting the MPs to raster format with grid cells of 8 meters, then computing the deformation gradient using neighborhood

algorithm. Given a 3x3 matrix, $\begin{bmatrix} z_1 & z_2 & z_3 \\ z_4 & z_5 & z_6 \\ z_7 & z_8 & z_9 \end{bmatrix}$,

algorithm estimates the gradient at the central grid cell (z_5) as the sum of the absolute values of the velocity variation in the east-west direction ($\frac{\partial z}{\partial x}$) and north-south direction ($\frac{\partial z}{\partial y}$) based on Eq. 1, Eq. 2, and Eq. 3 [6].

$$\frac{\partial z}{\partial x} = \frac{[(z_1 + 2z_4 + z_7) - (z_3 + 2z_6 + z_9)]}{8 * \text{grid spacing}} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial z}{\partial y} = \frac{[(z_1 + 2z_2 + z_3) - (z_7 + 2z_8 + z_9)]}{8 * \text{grid spacing}} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Gradient} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial x}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial z}{\partial y}\right)^2} \quad (3)$$

For each building, we compute its gradient and retain the value with the maximum gradient for utilization in the classification process.

Figure 1: Flowchart of the methodology.

- 3) We have developed a classification system for categorizing buildings based on their maximum gradient values, ranging from "Low" to "Very High" (Refer to Figure 2, Gradient legend to see the class boundaries). The gradient uncertainty is the primary factor in the classification, as it serves as a threshold for assigning the classes. To obtain the gradient standard deviation, we propagated the errors through the model using Monte Carlo simulation. We considered that the error sources are in the displacement velocity and the positioning of MPs [4], [5], [7]. A set of 200 Monte Carlo simulations were conducted, giving an estimated gradient standard deviation of around $0.05 \text{ mm} \cdot \text{yr}^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$. Utilizing the classification system, each identified building is assigned to a specific class, demonstrating the gradient intensity and potential damage level.

Figure 2 depicts an example of the proposed methodology steps from interpolation the deformation velocity of MPs within polygon, calculating the spatial gradient and finally classifying the building. As a resulting output, this tool generates a shapefile containing the identification and coordinates of buildings, as well as the maximum, mean, standard deviation, and orientation of the gradient. To facilitate the visualization of the outcomes, Geographic Information System (GIS) tools can be used.

Figure 2: Complete analysis workflow including rasterizing, gradient computation, and gradient intensity classification.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this research, we employed a proposed tool for the Catalunya region, using OpenStreetMap data for polygons and EGMS data for PSI displacement map. The EGMS displacement map is in ascending geometry from February 23, 2015, to December 24, 2021. Through the analysis of the spatial gradient of deformation for each building, this tool allows for the identification of buildings within urban areas that may be vulnerable to damage resulting from differential movements. Figure 4a depicts all the identified buildings in Catalunya. In order to check the precision of the procedure, we run an uncertainty analysis. Figure 3 shows the ratio of gradient-to-standard deviation and the density of MPS points. The X axis represents the number (density) within the identified buildings (polygons). The Y-axis, representing the ratio of gradient to standard deviation. When the ratio tends to 1, the standard deviation of the gradient is equivalent to the average value of the gradient. The ratio is below 1 when the number of MPs is below 15.

Figure 3: Ratio of the gradient and its standard deviation as a function of the MP number.

A total of 308 buildings were found to be at risk of damage. of these, 7.8% were classified as "Not reliable," 47.7% as "Low," 28.6% as "Medium," 14.3% as "High," and 2.2% as "Very High". Figure 4b concentrates on the Parets del Vallès area as an example, presenting its building differential deformation map. Most of the detected buildings have an intensity gradient ranging from "Low" to "Medium," while only one building is classified as "High". Figures 4c and 5d show the deformation along the LOS direction in Catalunya and the Parets del Vallès areas, respectively. Conducting field surveys can be used as a validation method to confirm the accuracy of identified buildings. Cracks in the exterior of structures are evidence of differential deformation.

4. CONCLUSION

Continuous monitoring for several years using SAR data and PSI technique gives us the opportunity to analyze the deformation gradient in both rural and urban areas, including a large number of buildings. The present research

Figure 4: Building differential deformation map in Catalunya.

analyses the gradient of local deformations that impact individual structures or buildings. As previously mentioned, European Ground Motion Service (EGMS) is the first monitoring application that aims to perform ground deformation monitoring over an entire EU continent, utilizing full-resolution processing of all Sentinel-1 images. Following the Copernicus data policy, the products of EGMS are free and open. The application of this tool starts with EGMS displacement map through the Catalunya area to generate building differential deformation map. We classified identified buildings according to their maximum gradient of deformation into five groups which show their gradient intensity. Structural damages such as fractures or cracks can be found among identified buildings associated with gradient intensity classes. To guarantee the detected buildings, we set the minimum number of MPs within polygons to 15. The differential deformation map serves as the first layer of information required for an in-depth analysis and risk assessment. By utilizing this map, beneficiaries can improve their ability to assure building safety and stability, contributing to a more comprehensive awareness of structural issues and supporting effective risk mitigation procedures.

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